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The eponymous totem Wolf (Boru, Bure, Biryuk, Vlats, Vlak, Wargur) in mythologies, epics, legends and folk traditions

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Resume. The article deals with the eponymous totem Wolf (Boru, Bure, Biryuk, Vlats, Vlak, Wulf), reflected in mythologies, epics, legends and folk traditions. Wolf as one of the most widespread and ancient totems, personifying strength, dexterity, cunning and collectivism. Totem Wolf is the creation of prehistoric times, when primitive birth lived in harmony with nature and the wild animal world.

Keywords: totem, eponym, Wolf (Boru, Bure, Biryuk, Wargur), nurse-wolf, wolf-counselor, dog.

Эпоним-тотем Волк (Бору, Бюре, Бирюк, Влъц, Влък, Wargur) в мифологиях, эпосах, легендах и народных преданиях

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается эпоним-тотем Волк (Бору, Бюре, Бирюк, Влъц, Влък, Wolf), отраженный в мифологиях, эпосах, легендах и народных преданиях. Волк как один из самых распространенных и древних тотемов, олицетворяющий силу, ловкость, хитроумность и коллективизм. Тотем Волк творение доисторического времени, когда первобытные роды жили в гармонии с природой и диким животным миром.

Ключевые слова: тотем, эпоним, Волк (Бору, Бюре, Бирюк, Wolf, Wargur), волчица-кормилица, волк-вожак, собака.

The nurse-wolf. Iakinf reports the tragic fate of House Hunnu, where, after the defeat by a neighboring unfriendly tribe, one ten-year-old boy remains alive. He will be nurtured by a she-wolf, and they will have ten sons. From them will appear special birth. Among them will be the Ashin clan [10, p. 257]. The myth of the wolves is found in the same way among the ancient Romans: "Verse 566. Mars is a wolf ... - According to Roman mythology, wolves were considered the sacred animal of the god Mars. Wolves raised the sons of Mars, the first founders of Rome - Romulus and Remus" [9]. "According to Plutarch, the day of the holiday has long been called "febrata". Among the Greeks, the holiday of Lycaea corresponds to it, which serves as evidence that, in ancient times, the comrades of Evandra moved it to Arkaadia here. This opinion is shared by everyone: the name of the holiday comes from the "she-wolf" [21, p. 75]. "In addition to the wolf festival of Lupercalia and the legend of the she-wolf feeding Romulus and Remus, different beliefs were associated with the wolves, talking about their role in ancient times" [15, p. 114]. Therefore, in addition to two major holidays, the ancient Romans had many different superstitious traditions in honor of wolves.

E. B. Taylor gives interesting examples of thought that one cannot but agree with. So, "Is it really true that the Roman twins were also accidentally really abandoned and fed by a nurse, who was called Lupa (translated from Latin - a she-wolf) ... Slavic folk tradition tells of a she-wolf and a dipper, who fed two supernatural twins: Valigor, who moved the mountains, and Vyrvidub tearing oaks with roots. Germany has its own legend of Dieterich, nicknamed Wolfditrich, by the name of its

wolf nurse. There is also a legend telling about Burt-Chino about a boy who was thrown into the lake, saved by a she-wolf and became the founder of the Turkish state" [24, p. 127]. The above-mentioned ethnic groups (Romans, Slavs, Germans, Turks) live in different parts of the Eurasian continent, but according to their own legends they are all interconnected with the identical archetype - the she-wolf-nurse. Apparently, "Tales of the wolf, traditional for the Turkic-Mongol tribes, could be brought to Europe by nomads from Asia. They also influenced the medieval European epic" [8, p. 330].

Wolf-counselor. "At dawn, a ray similar to the sun penetrated into the tent of Oguz-kagan. From that ray a gray-haired, gray-maned big wolf arose and said: "Now move with the army, Oguz-kagan. Bring people and Beks here, I will show you the way" [25, pp. 37, 46]. "According to the Uigur version ... not earlier than the VI-VII century. AD The Oguz Kagan, together with the Altun Kagan, accompanied as a counselor wolf (one of the totem animals of the ancient Turks) set off against the Urum beg, i.e. Roman "beg". It is, in all likelihood, a clash between the nomad Turks and Byzantium" [4, p. 39]. According to the scientist, this could happen in 576, and the most recent events reflected in the legend date back to no later than the 12th century. AD and ends with the liver-Polovtsian stages" [4, p. 40]. "In the Bashkir legends and traditions, the mythical wolf (court) acts as the leader of some tribes who moved to the Southern Urals" [11, p. 14]. Or, "the plot of the "wolf-counselor" is very close to the legend of the origin of the Samnite (ancient Italian) tribe of girpin (girpus wolf). Hirpins came to the territory they

conquered, led by a wolf (“the wolf, going up to him, became his companion and counselor”)¹ [1, p. 95].

In the Kyrgyz heroic epos “Manas”:

Kyzmatta jurgon kyrk chilten (Serving forty chiltens)

Bir silkinip birobu (One of them shook himself)

Kok boru bolup kalgany (And, turned into a blue wolf)

[26, p. 97].

In the epic, forty chiltens are forty human wolves. The epic does not say, however, perhaps these sacred forty-chiltens are representatives of the ancient forty-tribe Kyrgyz. They protect the still young, fragile Manas in difficult moments of life. A human Chilten could turn into a wolf and vice versa. (Chilten, possibly, consists of the eponyms Az¹, El², Ton³). It is noteworthy that the epic talks about blue wolves that could be identified with historical similar ancient stunt totems.

Boru bolgon biz dedi ... (We are Wolves-Wolves ...)

Kyzir Ilyas degen bar, (There is a certain Khzir Ilyas.)

Sizdi kyrk kundon beri izdedi. (He was looking for you for forty days.)

Kirk Chiltene Degen Biz Dedi (We are forty Chiltens)

[27, p. 114]

Here, forty Chiltens tell Manas that Hzir Ilyas searched for him for forty days. This could mean that the ancient spiritual world of the forty-tribe Kyrgyz (in the person of forty Chiltens) collaborated with the subsequent spiritual and religious world (in the person of Khzir Ilyas). So, in the life of the ancient Kyrgyz tribes there was a tribal totem wolf, it performed a dominant function.

The wolf as an eponymous totem. The Dulgasiyans of the House of Dulga wore “banners with a golden wolves head. The bodyguards were called Fuli, which also means in the Mongolian language: wolf, sign that they remember their origin from the wolf.” According to historical data, “The Eastern House of Dulga in 535-745 had twenty-one khan” [10, pp. 266, 269]. The Mongolian chronicle “The Secret Legend” reports on the birth of Genghis Khan: “The ancestor of Genghis Khan was Borte Chino, born by the permission of the Higher Heaven. His wife was Goa-Maral.” Translated from the Mongolian Burt-Chino - “gray wolf”, Goa-Maral - “beautiful doe” [13, p. 179]. “Asperukh - Esperukh - Ispereh - the name of the Bulgarian khan, son of Kubrat: es bëri comrade wolf” [2, p. 30]. However, it seems to us that in this case the historical Asparuh is not a “comrade wolf”, but an eponym AzBeruOk (AzWolfArrow), i.e. involved archon-eponym Az. “Er Bori: er + bori “wolf”, Er Buqa: buga “bull” [18, p. 185]. Here a combination of lexemes er and bori in word formation (“wolf”) draws attention.

Biryuk is a wolf. “Biryuk (in Tatar Byuryu) conversational lone wolf. Etymological dictionaries unanimously bring this word together with the Tatar bure, the Kumyk beryu wolf” [3, p. 5]. In Russian scientific works of the XIX century: “Wolf lupus: the word pre-Slavic; it is close to German Wulf, lat. lupus, san. varkos. Regional names: rus. biryuk volk (Dal, Nosov)” [5, p. 195]. Here the word

“wolf” is considered pre-Slavic, it is related to the German, Latin, Greek, Sanskrit variants. However, the main thing, according to Dal and Nosov, the ancient name of the wolf is biryuk, i.e. it is consonant with the Turkic beru (wolf).

“Vladimir agreed and ordered the priests, or heralds, in his camp to click hunters for fights” [12, p. 109]. Here, apparently, I mean the heralds-heralds, who, according to the ancient tradition, called out rivals for competitions with wolf howls. It is known that when the Bulgarian Konstantin Philosopher (Cyril) went to the Khazars, “when he prayed at the first hour, the Hungarians attacked him, howling like wolves, wanting to kill him” [23, p. 78]. Or, “Ovlur or Vlur can be successfully explained from the ancient Türkic root of Ulu - “howl like a wolf, whence ulu-r is “howling like a wolf, which coincides with the comparison between the Vlur-Ovlur and the wolf in the “Word” (“then Vlur vkom potech”)” [17, p. 160]. It seems that Vlur-Ovlur was from the Beru tribe (wolf), and accompanied Igor in an imaginary flight at the instigation of Konchak himself.

“At the end of VII - beginning of VI century. BC. the first Greek colonies appeared in the Lower Pobuzhie and the Lower Dnieper, of which Borisfen (Berezan) is the earliest” [22, p. 5]. “Berezan and Snake - these are the names of two islands in the north-west of the Black Sea that belong to our country. The name “Berezan” comes from the Turkic Biryuk of Yuzen Ada, that is: “An island at the confluence of the Wolf River” [14, p. 169]. Or, “the Biryusins lived in the subaiga area of the Kuznetsk Alatau (in Khakass “Purus”), who united under their name seeks: Kharga, Khuy, Khoby, Khizyl Khaya, Tayas” [6, p. 87]. According to this information, the ethnonym biryus (or purus) is identical to the totem beru (wolf).

Varangians-wolves. “Wolves, wolves! - shouted Rolav. - We paid a full tribute! And you burned the village, captured people! My father’s blood is on you!” [19, p. 13]. In the work of art, the Novgorodian guy fiercely defends himself against the attacking Varangians, calling them, as it seems to us, a Varangian clan totem (“wolves”). “A large section of her article (L. Grot. - A. E.) is devoted to exposing linguists and historians, who root the word (Varyag. - A. E.) First to the Old Norse vargur - “wolf”, and later to var - “water” [16, p. 194]. Nevertheless, some linguists and historians believed that the etymology of the word “Varangian” is elevated to the lexeme vargur (wolf). G.Z. Bayer, trying to prove the Swedish origin of the Varangians, argued that “Scandia is called Vergion from some and that it means the island of wolves, which in the ancient language does not always mean a wolf, but a robber and an enemy”. O. Verelius in his note to the Hervard saga: “from the great robbery at sea, because wolves (Wargur) are those who rob and devastate both on land and at sea” [16, p. 195]. It seems to us that those “robbers and enemies”, and, “those who rob and devastate both on land and at sea” are the ancient Scandinavian ethnic groups who wore the totem “wolf”.

¹ Эпоним Аз в исторических источниках и эпических сказаниях // Евразийское научное объединение, №12 (58), декабрь, 2019.

<https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=41828094>

² Эпические теонимы Илайя, Алда таала: предшественники, параллели, аналогии // Евразийское научное

объединение, №10 (56), октябрь, 2019.

<https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=41385415>

³ Эпоним Тон (Тон, Чон, Чон, Джон, Жан) и эпические параллели, аналогии // Евразийское научное объединение, №1 (59), январь, 2020.

<https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=42434021>

It is known that there are no totems of a global scale, named from dogs and horses, the closest pets of people. Most likely, they are late phenomena in human life: dogs and horses were then still wild animals (dogs were still wolves, horses were not yet tamed). According to archeology, dogs are 20-30 thousand years old (according to some sources 100 thousand) years. They have their own gene ("love for people at the genetic level"), which was different from wolves (although the DNA matches). "In general, a dog is considered to be the oldest domestic animal, but it appears for the first time only during the Neolithic period. Wild species of dogs of the Quaternary period represented various races of jackals and wolves ..." [20, p. 534]. Perhaps the dog is a relatively late companion in the primitive life of a rational person. It seems that by that time people had a

symbiotic understanding of the world, totems were filled with the names of wild animals. It turns out that the most ancient totems are a wolf, a bear, a lion, a swan for at least 10,000 thousand years.

So, the wolf is one of the most widespread and main totems of the peoples of the world. So, "the wolf was a totem of many Indo-European tribes. The unity of the wolves in the pack, the distribution of functions within the pack (the "laws" of the pack) reminded the ancient people of their own collective, which led to ideas about the relationship of people with wolves" [7, p. 54]. In ancient clans and tribes, the wolf totem, apparently, personified strength, dexterity, cunning and collectivism. And it is no accident that most genera of the first intelligent people chose this powerful and formidable totem.

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